

NDAC/LO/004

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Test of IDT Preprocessing Algorithm1. Introduction

Preprocessing of IDT data in the NDAC terminology means that the five signal parameters $b_1 - b_5$ ($\propto$ Fourier components) and their covariance are estimated for each star and each frame. Instead of 2400 photometric samples we then have about 80 floating point numbers per frame (on the average), corresponding to compression roughly by a factor 10. In principle the compressed data should contain practically all relevant information, so that any parameter that can be estimated from the raw data can almost equally well be estimated from the compressed data.

That this is actually the case has not been demonstrated yet. In fact, numerical experiments reported by the FAST Consortium (FAST Proposal, Technical Annex 3.1) cast serious doubt on the method.

We report here some first results of Monte Carlo tests of the NDAC preprocessing and location estimation algorithms (NDAC Proposal, Annex A, pp. 27 - 29). The tests indicate that locations estimated via compressed data are virtually identical to those estimated directly from raw data; no increased variance is observed.

2. Signal models

It is assumed that the photon counts N_k obey Poisson statistics with expectations

$$E(N_k) = B\Delta t + I_0\Delta t \left[1 + M_1 \cos(H_k + p) + M_2 \cos(2H_k + 2p - v_2) \right] \quad (1)$$

where Δt , B , I_0 , M_1 , M_2 , v_2 , and p are given parameters, and

H_k is the known reference phase of each sample. We are only interested in the location (phase) parameter p , which is estimated in three different ways:

A. Unconstrained estimate (= preprocessing)

No a priori information on B , I_0 , M_1 , M_2 , v_2 , or p is assumed. The signal model is

$$I_k(\underline{b}_A) = b_1 + b_2 \cos(H_k + b_3) + b_4 \cos(2H_k + 2b_3) + b_5 \sin(2H_k + 2b_3) \quad (2)$$

Maximum likelihood estimation gives $\hat{\underline{b}}_A$ and $\underline{F}_A^{-1} \propto \text{Cov}(\hat{\underline{b}}_A)$, from which we extract

$$P_A = (\hat{\underline{b}}_A)_3 \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_A = (\underline{F}_A^{-1})_{33}^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

B. Constrained estimate directly from raw data

$m = M_2/M_1$ and v_2 are assumed to be known, so only three signal parameters need to be estimated:

$$I_k(\underline{b}_B) = b_1 + b_2 \left[\cos(H_k + b_3) + m \cos(2H_k + 2b_3 - v_2) \right] \quad (4)$$

Application of ML gives $\hat{\underline{b}}_B$ and $\underline{F}_B^{-1} \propto \text{Cov}(\hat{\underline{b}}_B)$ from which

$$P_B = (\hat{\underline{b}}_B)_3 \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_B = (\underline{F}_B^{-1})_{33}^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

C. Constrained estimate via compressed data

Again m and v_2 are assumed to be known, but the three signal parameters b_1, b_3 are obtained from $\hat{\underline{b}}_A$ and $\underline{F}_A^{-1}$ according to

$$\hat{\underline{b}}_C = \hat{\underline{b}}_A - \underline{F}_A^{-1} \underline{C}' (\underline{C} \underline{F}_A^{-1} \underline{C}')^{-1} \underline{C} \hat{\underline{b}}_A \quad (6)$$

where $\underline{C}$ is the constraint matrix. Also,

$$\text{Cov}(\hat{\underline{b}}_C) \propto \underline{F}_C^{-1} = \underline{F}_A^{-1} - \underline{F}_A^{-1} \underline{C}' (\underline{C} \underline{F}_A^{-1} \underline{C}')^{-1} \underline{C} \underline{F}_A^{-1} \quad (7)$$

This gives us p_C and σ_C .

3. Simulations

P_A , P_B , P_C , σ_A , σ_B , and σ_C were computed for 100 different realisations of $\{N_k\}$ with the following input data:

grid period	s	=	1.1	as
scanning speed	v	=	150	as/s
sampling frequency	$1/\Delta t$	=	1200	Hz
modulation coefficients	M_1	=	0.687	
	M_2	=	0.308	
phase shift	v_2	=	0	
background count rate	B	=	29	Hz
stellar count rate	I_0	=	1780	Hz

Each experiment generated 720 photometric samples (0.6 s) spread out over a 2 second frame in 10 equidistant portions. The reference phases used in the ML fittings, $\{H_k\}$, were the true ones; i.e. no scanning speed error was assumed.

4. Results

If $p_{.i}$, $\sigma_{.i}$, $i = 1$ to 100 are the results of individual experiments, we computed ($n = 100$)

- the average errors,

$$\bar{p}_{.} = n^{-1} \sum_i p_{.i}$$

- the rms errors,

$$p_{.rms} = [n^{-1} \sum_i p_{.i}^2]^{1/2}$$

- the average mean errors,

$$\bar{\sigma}_{.} = n^{-1} \sum_i \sigma_{.i}$$

- the dispersion of mean errors, $\delta\sigma_{.} = [(n-1)^{-1} \sum_i (\sigma_{.i} - \bar{\sigma}_{.})^2]^{1/2}$

The table below gives the numerical results with uncertainties ($\pm 1\sigma$) estimated as $p_{.rms}/\sqrt{n}$ (for $\bar{p}_{.}$); $p_{.rms}/\sqrt{(2n)}$ (for $p_{.rms}$); and $\delta\sigma_{.}/\sqrt{n}$ (for $\bar{\sigma}_{.}$). All numbers are in mas.

Method of estimation	$\bar{P}$.	P.rms	$\bar{\sigma}$.	$\delta\sigma$.	Expected mean error*
A - unconstrained	-0.95 ± 1.06	10.55 ± 0.75	10.05 ± 0.07	0.67	10.09 mas
B - constrained (direct)	-0.37 ± 0.91	9.04 ± 0.64	8.76 ± 0.05	0.52	8.80 mas
C - constrained (via A)	-0.32 ± 0.91	9.01 ± 0.64	8.82 ± 0.07	0.71	8.80 mas

* from computing F_1^{-1} with true parameters instead of estimated

5. Conclusions

From the agreement between $p_{B\text{rms}}$ and $p_{C\text{rms}}$ we conclude that the intermediate preprocessing does not increase the variance of the location estimate. This is seen even better from the statistics of the difference $p_C - p_B$, which has an rms value of only 0.33 mas. (In other words: the correlation between p_C and p_B is 0.99933.)

It is also seen that B and C give almost identical estimates of the mean error, and that these estimates are in good agreement both with observed rms errors and expected mean errors.

From these very limited experiments it appears that the proposed preprocessing method does not degrade the results or introduce biases.